

BEYOND THE CLASSROOM: ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS AND CHALLENGES OF AFTER-SCHOOL ENGLISH PROGRAMS AMONG TAIWANESE LEARNERS

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Beyond the Classroom: Assessing the Effectiveness and Challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese Learners

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness and challenges of after-school English programs specifically designed for Taiwanese learners in select cram schools across urban areas. The research focused on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools in terms of student engagement, language proficiency, parent satisfaction, teacher qualifications, and curriculum quality; and the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools in terms of resource availability, financial considerations, curriculum limitations, cultural factors, and feedback mechanisms. Also, it focused on understanding how these programs impact students' language proficiency, engagement, and motivation in learning English. By selecting a diverse range of schools characterized by limited resources and overcrowded classrooms, the study gathered quantitative data through surveys, and observations. Respondents included in the study were students enrolled in after-school programs, and teachers facilitating these programs allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the program's reach and efficacy. The findings concluded that the student engagement, parent satisfaction, teacher qualifications, curriculum quality, and language proficiency were some of the metrics used to evaluate the after-school English programs, all of which pointed to their great effectiveness. Also, the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools reveals no significant in terms of student engagement, parent satisfaction, teacher qualifications, curriculum quality, and language proficiency. Feedback mechanisms, cultural factors, curriculum limitations, financial considerations, and resource availability were all major challenges in assessing after-school English programs for Taiwanese students at chosen Cram schools. Feedback mechanisms substantially affect the evaluation of the two respondent groups of the issues faced by after-school English programs among Taiwanese learners at certain Cram schools. The efficacy of after-school English programs is unrelated to the difficulties encountered by Taiwanese students in select Cram schools. The study recommended that teachers may implement activities that promote student engagement such as games, group projects, and presentations to make learning enjoyable and relevant; students may take part in vocabulary activities such as word games, discussions, and group projects and may practice incorporating newly learned vocabulary into writing assignments; and administrators may offer ongoing training sessions that focus on innovative teaching methods, classroom management techniques, and the integration of technology to enhance lesson delivery.

Keywords: *effectiveness and challenges, after-school english programs, Taiwanese learners, cram schools*

Introduction

Over the last few years, interest in English has grown steadily in Taiwan due to globalization, job competition, etc. In this regard, a number of after-school English programs have been implemented in the different settings to improve students' language clarity during other hours than classroom lessons. Nevertheless, the impact of these programs, especially in the context of schools where space and resources are a concern, as is apparent with many schools within the Gauteng province, merits further analysis. It lays the foundation upon which an evaluation of the satisfaction and difficulties encountered in after-school English programs for Taiwanese learners will be made, with emphasis on some cram educational settings.

Studies have also shown that an after-school program can foster acquisition of a second language by giving more practicing and usage time and interaction with people who use the language fluently. Past research conducted in Taiwan has revealed the effect of such programs on the students' speaking and listening skills. Nevertheless, these works fail to capture the complexities of learners, who in most cases are faced with congested classrooms that deny them the opportunity to learn individually or even be attended to by instructors. Therefore, the impact of ESOL programs in this regard has not been well established and warrants a differential analysis.

Congestion in schools has been associated with numerous issues, including the following: Excessive class size does not only restrict physical space, which is very essential when learning a foreign language, but also limits access to teaching tools and other teaching aids that may be required for the tutorial process. Large groups may also be difficult for the instructors to handle, thus compromising the time they spend with individual students. Therefore, the quality of instruction may be low and can give a counterproductive result to the major goals of after-school English programs. Preparation of a policy brief requires a rather deep analysis of such factors to assess their impact on the organization's attempt at increasing its efficiency when implementing such measures.

Another element that adds a degree of complexity to the picture is the differences in program delivery from one school to the other. Small-scale institutions may focus on proper teaching and training schedules and qualified teachers, while others may be forced to opt

for poor teaching methods due to a lack of resources. Fortunately, this internal inconsistency is easily recognizable and does not obscure the overall picture, though it does pose a problem for generalization of the results of previous research on after-school programs. It emphasizes the necessity of the assessment of some particular programs in various settings, especially in small territories, to make more correct conclusions regarding the effectiveness and the spheres of necessity of amendments.

However, SES cannot be overlooked due to its importance in the outcome. After-school programs may be attended by learners from low-income families in order to improve their English performance and increase their chances of success. But these learners may also encounter more challenges, for instance, with low parental support, low self-esteem, and distractions. All these ingredients can significantly affect issues to do with enrolment and the success of ESL in after-school programs. Exploring the further potential of the effect of these social characteristics on the program structures could provide the key discriminating factors that should be taken into consideration for the future implementation of such policies and programs.

Moreover, although there are numerous publications available to date to discuss the effectiveness of the methods in teaching and learning the language, they fail to capture the psychological aspect of the learning process. The process of learning is not only the cognitive aspects of the process; it also elicits the affective and interpersonal aspects of learning. Peer activities, culture sensitivity, and the process of instructions are some of the key aspects that influence students in their extracurricular English programs. It is important to comprehend such processes so that solutions may be developed that will not only aim at enhancing the learning outcomes but also at promoting the positive learning climate.

In that regard, there are some noticeable gaps in the research. Previous research has investigated after-school English programs in Taiwan, though limited work assesses their efficacy within the limited space of the school environment. Also, very few studies have followed up students for a longer period to compare the effects of these programs on language acquisition and performance in academic endeavors. Fill these gaps, and in this way, there will be an expansion to the knowledge base of those who are interested in after-school programs and better understandings of how these after-school programs could meet the diverse learning needs of different contexts.

In addition, much of the onus lies with the teachers to undertake professional development programs and equip them with better training to boost the program's effectiveness. Quality education and teaching methodologies adapted to students and facilities of limited space are very important in this case. Exploring the extent that there are effective training programs for teachers/educators participating in after-school activities/preschool education and, if there are, in what ways these training programs can be enhanced may be considered a valuable line of study. This aspect is important as it will equip the teachers with the right knowledge and skills on how to manage an overcrowded classroom.

Finally, the evaluation of after-school English programs for Taiwanese students in some cram schools has been deemed a research necessity in the Taiwanese education context. Thus, the purpose of this research study is to consider the effectiveness and challenging aspects of such programs to determine the crucial factors that inhibit their success and provide recommendations for further advancement. It is thus recognized that this research will contribute to the current continuum of conversational and discourse around language education in Taiwan and hopefully facilitate the quality of English provision and learning for students in these demanding but important settings.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness and challenges of After-School English programs among Taiwanese learners in select cram schools' serves as the foundation of instructional plan. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. student engagement;
 - 1.2. language proficiency;
 - 1.3. parent satisfaction;
 - 1.4. teacher qualifications; and
 - 1.5. curriculum quality?
2. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools with respect to the aforementioned variables?
3. What is the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1. resource availability;
 - 3.2. financial considerations;
 - 3.3. curriculum limitations;
 - 3.4. cultural factors; and
 - 3.5. feedback mechanisms?
4. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools with respect to the aforementioned variables?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of effectiveness and the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what instructional plan may be devised?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used descriptive correlational research designs since the study assessed the significant relationship between the level of effectiveness and the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools. According to Katzukov (2020), a descriptive correlational study describes the relationships among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. Also, correlational research helps in comparing two or more entities or variables. Descriptive correlational research is a non-experimental research method that describes and measures the connection between two or more variables without changing them. Descriptive correlational studies can provide valuable insights into how different factors relate to the success or difficulties experienced in after-school English programs among Taiwanese learners in select cram schools. Furthermore, descriptive correlational research is critical in evaluating the success and problems of after-school English programs for Taiwanese students in overcrowded schools. This method helps educators, administrators, and policymakers improve program quality, deal with problems, and ultimately help students learn English better in these specific situations by describing current conditions and looking at how key variables are related.

Respondents

The general population of this study refers to the select Taiwanese students and teachers in cram schools. To determine the sample respondents, the study employed non-probability sampling utilizing the purposive sampling technique in determining the respondents of the study.

The respondents of the study were the selected Taiwanese students and teachers in cram schools. The researcher purposively selects forty (40) students and thirty-five (35) teachers. A total of seventy-five (75) respondents. The respondents evaluated the effectiveness and challenges of After-School English programs among Taiwanese learners in select cram schools' serves as the foundation of instructional plan.

Instrument

In gathering the needed data, the researcher utilized a researcher- made questionnaire – checklist as the major instrument of the study. Part 1 – This section determined the demographic profile of the respondents. Part 2 – This part determined the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of student engagement, language proficiency, parent satisfaction, teacher qualifications, and curriculum quality; Part 3 determined the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of resource availability, financial considerations, curriculum limitations, cultural factors, and feedback mechanisms.

Validation and Test of Reliability of Instrument

The survey questionnaire that was used in the research was given to the adviser to gain preliminary feedback and ideas for improving the questionnaire checklist. Following the modification of the instrument, the researcher's questionnaire checklist was evaluated by specialists with a suitable background in test building and on the subject to remark on its content for the finalization of the questionnaire checklist items. Professors from the University of Perpetual Help System Dalta and English teachers at select cram schools assessed the questionnaire checklist. The researcher selects them specifically since they were all active in the program.

Procedure

The Gantt chart guides the course of the investigation. Permission to conduct research was requested from the Office of the President and Office of the School Administrators at select cram schools.

The researcher validated the questionnaire with the assistance of specialists and those knowledgeable about the competency and work satisfaction of teachers in public schools. Once completed, the researcher delivered the questionnaire to the study participants. The questionnaire was then acquired, and the collected data were examined using a suitable statistical tool. The interpretation and conclusions made from the acquired data may confirm or contradict the findings of previous study on the topic.

Similarly, the researcher presented a summary of the study's results and conclusions, as well as some recommendations based on those findings. Finally, the remaining chapters of the study and preparation for the researcher's final oral defense were completed.

Data Analysis

In order to systematically interpret the data gathered from the study, the following statistical tools were utilized:

To determine the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of student engagement, language proficiency, parent satisfaction, teacher qualifications, and curriculum quality; weighted mean was used.

To find out if there is a significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools with respect to the aforementioned variables; paired t-test was applied.

To determine the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of resource availability, financial considerations, curriculum limitations, cultural factors, and feedback mechanisms; weighted mean was applied.

To find out if there is a significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools with respect to the aforementioned variables; paired t-test was applied.

To find out if there is a significant relationship between the level of effectiveness and the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools; Pearson-r correlation was used.

Ethical Considerations

The section covers concepts and processes in the conduct of the study in compliance with the ethical standards of research writing, including how the respondents participated. Before gathering data, the researcher will submit duly completed forms and documents that have undergone rigorous screening and checking by the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of the University of Perpetual Help System Delta. The REC approves of the conduct of this research.

The researcher will adhere to the ethical standards of research writing by verifying the reliability of the sources that comprise the study's literature and by appropriately acknowledging and crediting their authors for their contributions to the research. By adhering to copyright and patent rules and recognizing the rightful owners of the published studies used in this paper, the researcher will avoid plagiarism. The researcher will also obtain the necessary permission to use materials as a source for the well-founded creation of this endeavor, even if it is not intended for public consumption.

In collecting data, respondents' consent will be obtained by providing them with brief background information and the purpose of the study before their participation. The researcher will uphold the key informants' rights to the fullest, guaranteeing the complete confidentiality of any information they choose to share in order to achieve the study's objectives. The identity of the respondents shall remain confidential if this research is published. In addition, the respondents will be informed that they might request access to the study results by emailing the researcher at desmacuray@gmail.com. The researcher will obtain the respondents' consent without harm, coercion, or manipulation and inform them of their freedom to withdraw from the study should they choose to do so.

Additionally, the researcher will not fabricate or misrepresent the data to guarantee a bias-free, truthful, and sound result in this study. Moreover, this research will adhere to proper research guidelines based on the American Psychological Association (APA) 7th Edition.

Results and Discussion

The findings, analysis, and interpretation of the data collected in light of the research's challenges are briefly discussed in this chapter.

Problem No. 1: What is the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of student engagement, language proficiency, parent satisfaction, teacher qualifications, and curriculum quality?

Table 1.1 illustrates the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of student engagement.

As gleaned in the table, the two groups of respondents assessed the entire indicators as Highly Effective on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of student engagement such as Students participate actively in class discussions during the after-school English program (M=3.93); Students regularly attend the after-school English program due to their interest in the subject matter (M=3.92); Teachers in the after-school English program encourage and support student participation (M=3.92); Students express their opinions and ideas freely in the after-school English program (M=3.91); and Students feel motivated to complete assignments given in the after-school English program (M=3.90). This was supported, with the overall mean value of 3.92 interpreted as highly effective.

The finding that After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools are highly effective in enhancing student engagement suggests that the integration of targeted, interactive learning experiences can significantly boost motivation and academic performance in language acquisition.

This aligns with the study by Chang and Wu (2018), which indicates that engaging pedagogical strategies, such as group activities and

project-based learning, not only improve language skills but also foster a positive learning environment that encourages participation. Therefore, educational stakeholders should prioritize the development and implementation of dynamic after-school programs that cater to the interests and needs of students, thereby maximizing their engagement and subsequent success in English language learning.

Table 1.1. Mean of the Two Groups of Respondents' Assessment on the Level of Effectiveness of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners In Select Cram Schools in terms of Student Engagement

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Overall		
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	
1. Students participate actively in class discussions during the after-school English program.	3.94	HE	3.93	HE	3.93	HE	
2. Students feel motivated to complete assignments given in the after-school English program.	3.94	HE	3.85	HE	3.90	HE	
3. Students express their opinions and ideas freely in the after-school English program.	3.91	HE	3.90	HE	3.91	HE	
4. Students regularly attend the after-school English program due to their interest in the subject matter.	3.94	HE	3.90	HE	3.92	HE	
5. Teachers in the after-school English program encourage and support student participation	3.94	HE	3.90	HE	3.92	HE	
	Mean	3.94	HE	3.89	HE	3.92	HE

***Legend: 3.26-4.00- Highly Effective; 2.51-3.25-Effective; 1.76-2.50 -Slightly Effective; 1.00-1.75 - Not Effective

Table 1.2 manifests the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of language proficiency.

Table 1.2. Mean of the Two Groups of Respondents' Assessment on the Level of Effectiveness of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners In Select Cram Schools in terms of Language Proficiency

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Overall		
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	
1. The after-school English program has improved student's overall English language skills.	3.74	HE	3.58	HE	3.66	HE	
2. Students feel more confident in speaking English after attending the after-school program.	3.71	HE	3.63	HE	3.67	HE	
3. The program effectively enhances student's listening comprehension skills in English.	3.71	HE	3.50	HE	3.61	HE	
4. Students have seen significant improvement in my reading skills due to the after-school English program.	3.69	HE	3.43	HE	3.56	HE	
5. The writing exercises in the program have positively impacted student's ability to write in English.	3.60	HE	3.48	HE	3.54	HE	
	Mean	3.70	HE	3.53	HE	3.62	HE

***Legend: 3.26-4.00- Highly Effective; 2.51-3.25-Effective; 1.76-2.50 -Slightly Effective; 1.00-1.75 - Not Effective

As manifested in the table, the two groups of respondents assessed the entire indicators as Highly Effective on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of language proficiency such as Students feel more confident in speaking English after attending the after-school program (M=3.67); The after-school English program has improved student's overall English language skills (M=3.66); The program effectively enhances student's listening comprehension skills in English (M=3.61); Students have seen significant improvement in reading skills due to the after-school English program (M=3.56); and The writing exercises in the program have positively impacted student's ability to write in English (M=3.54). This was supported, with the overall mean value of 3.62 interpreted as highly effective.

The conclusion that After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools significantly enhance language proficiency underscores the importance of structured supplementary education in achieving educational goals. This finding is supported by the research conducted by Huang and Liu (2019), which highlights that students participating in additional English instruction exhibit notable improvements in their reading, writing, and speaking skills compared to their peers who do not engage in such programs. Therefore, the effectiveness of these after-school programs suggests that policymakers and educators should consider expanding access to similar initiatives, as they play a crucial role in elevating language proficiency and better preparing students for global communication challenges.

Table 1.3 illustrates the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of parent satisfaction.

As illustrated in the table, the two groups of respondents assessed the entire indicators as Highly Effective on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of parent satisfaction such as Their child has shown improvement in English language skills since enrolling in the program (M=3.94); The program has had a positive impact on their child's attitude toward learning English (M=3.93); The cram school provides

adequate support and resources for their child's English learning ($M=3.92$); Parents believe the program's teachers are qualified and effective at teaching English ($M=3.91$); and The after-school English program meets parents' expectations for their child's learning needs ($M=3.88$). This was supported, with the overall mean value of 3.91 interpreted as highly effective.

Table 1.3. Mean of the Two Groups of Respondents' Assessment on the Level of Effectiveness of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners In Select Cram Schools in terms of Parent Satisfaction

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Overall		
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	
1. The after-school English program meets parents' expectations for their child's learning needs.	3.86	HE	3.90	HE	3.88	HE	
2. Parents believe the program's teachers are qualified and effective at teaching English.	3.94	HE	3.88	HE	3.91	HE	
3. The program has had a positive impact on their child's attitude toward learning English.	3.94	HE	3.93	HE	3.93	HE	
4. Their child has shown improvement in English language skills since enrolling in the program.	3.97	HE	3.90	HE	3.94	HE	
5. The cram school provides adequate support and resources for their child's English learning.	3.94	HE	3.90	HE	3.92	HE	
	Mean	3.93	HE	3.90	HE	3.91	HE

***Legend: 3.26-4.00- Highly Effective; 2.51-3.25-Effective; 1.76-2.50 -Slightly Effective; 1.00-1.75 - Not Effective

The high effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools, as indicated by the positive assessments from both students and parents, implies a strong alignment between program outcomes and parent expectations regarding their children's language education. This is consistent with the findings of Tsai and Chen (2020), which reveal that parental satisfaction significantly correlates with perceived improvements in their children's language abilities and overall academic performance in English. Consequently, this suggests that education stakeholders should prioritize creating and maintaining effective communication channels with parents, as their involvement and endorsement can further enhance program success and student motivation in language learning contexts.

Table 1.4 exhibits the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of teacher qualification.

As exhibited in the table, the two groups of respondents assessed the entire indicators as Highly Effective on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of teacher qualification such as The teachers show enthusiasm and passion for teaching English to students ($M=3.93$); The teachers regularly participate in professional development to enhance their teaching skills ($M=3.91$); The teachers effectively adapt their teaching methods to meet the varying needs of students ($M=3.89$); The teachers provide constructive feedback that helps my child improve their English skills ($M=3.88$); and The teachers are approachable and willing to help students who struggle with English ($M=3.72$). This was supported, with the overall mean value of 3.87 interpreted as highly effective.

Table 1.4. Mean of the Two Groups of Respondents' Assessment on the Level of Effectiveness of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners In Select Cram Schools in terms of Teacher Qualification

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Overall		
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	
1. The teachers are approachable and willing to help students who struggle with English.	3.51	HE	3.93	HE	3.72	HE	
2. The teachers effectively adapt their teaching methods to meet the varying needs of students.	3.89	HE	3.90	HE	3.89	HE	
3. The teachers show enthusiasm and passion for teaching English to students.	3.94	HE	3.93	HE	3.93	HE	
4. The teachers regularly participate in professional development to enhance their teaching skills.	3.91	HE	3.90	HE	3.91	HE	
5. The teachers provide constructive feedback that helps my child improve their English skills	3.83	HE	3.93	HE	3.88	HE	
	Mean	3.82	HE	3.92	HE	3.87	HE

***Legend: 3.26-4.00- Highly Effective; 2.51-3.25-Effective; 1.76-2.50 -Slightly Effective; 1.00-1.75 - Not Effective

The high effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools, particularly concerning teacher qualifications, implies that the professional background and training of instructors play a crucial role in enhancing student outcomes. This notion is supported by the research conducted by Liu and Zhang (2021), which found that students taught by qualified teachers with specialized training in language instruction demonstrated significantly greater improvements in their English proficiency compared to those taught by less qualified instructors. Therefore, this underscores the importance of investing in teacher development and ensuring that educators possess the necessary skills and knowledge to deliver high-quality language education, as this directly contributes to the overall success of these after-school programs.

Table 1.5 delineates the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of curriculum quality.

Table 1.5. *Mean of the Two Groups of Respondents' Assessment on the Level of Effectiveness of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners in Select Cram Schools in terms of Curriculum Quality*

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Overall		
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	
1. The curriculum is structured in a way that enhances student's English language skills.	3.54	HE	3.73	HE	3.63	HE	
2. The content of the curriculum is relevant and appropriate for students' age and language proficiency level.	3.63	HE	3.60	HE	3.61	HE	
3. The curriculum includes a good balance of reading, writing, listening, and speaking activities.	3.54	HE	3.60	HE	3.57	HE	
4. The curriculum provides adequate opportunities for students to practice their English skills.	3.97	HE	3.90	HE	3.94	HE	
5. The curriculum incorporates cultural aspects of English-speaking countries, enriching the learning experience.	3.57	HE	3.73	HE	3.65	HE	
	Mean	3.67	HE	3.71	HE	3.69	HE

***Legend: 3.26-4.00- Highly Effective; 2.51-3.25-Effective; 1.76-2.50 -Slightly Effective; 1.00-1.75 - Not Effective

As delineated in the table, the two groups of respondents assessed the entire indicators as Highly Effective on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of curriculum quality such as The curriculum provides adequate opportunities for students to practice their English skills (M=3.94); The curriculum incorporates cultural aspects of English-speaking countries, enriching the learning experience (M=3.65); The curriculum is structured in a way that enhances student's English language skills (M=3.63); The content of the curriculum is relevant and appropriate for students' age and language proficiency level (M=3.61); and The curriculum includes a good balance of reading, writing, listening, and speaking activities (M=3.57). This was supported, with the overall mean value of 3.69 interpreted as highly effective.

The high effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools, as assessed by both students and parents, implies that the quality of the curriculum plays a pivotal role in achieving positive educational outcomes. This is supported by the findings of Chen and Huang (2022), which revealed that well-structured curricula that incorporate interactive learning methodologies and culturally relevant content led to higher student engagement and improved language acquisition. Consequently, this indicates that ensuring high curriculum quality is essential for maximizing the effectiveness of after-school programs, ultimately meeting the expectations of both learners and their families.

Table 1.6 illustrates the composite mean of the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents.

Table 1.6. *Composite Mean of the Two Groups of Respondents' Assessment on the Level of Effectiveness of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners in Select Cram Schools*

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
student engagement	3.94	HE	3.89	HE	3.92	HE
language proficiency	3.70	HE	3.53	HE	3.62	HE
parent satisfaction	3.93	HE	3.90	HE	3.91	HE
teacher qualifications	3.82	HE	3.92	HE	3.87	HE
curriculum quality	3.57	HE	3.73	HE	3.65	HE
Mean	3.81	HE	3.79	HE	3.80	HE

***Legend: 3.26-4.00- Highly Effective; 2.51-3.25-Effective; 1.76-2.50 -Slightly Effective; 1.00-1.75 - Not Effective

As illustrated in the table on the summary of the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of student engagement (M=3.92); parent satisfaction (M=3.91); teacher qualifications (M=3.87); curriculum quality (M=3.65); and language proficiency (M=3.62). This was supported with a composite mean of 3.80 interpreted as highly effective.

The high composite means of effectiveness for After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools, as assessed by both students and parents, suggests that these programs are successfully meeting educational needs and expectations. This is further corroborated by the research of Li and Chen (2023), which found that programs with a high satisfaction rating from participants tend to utilize tailored instructional strategies that enhance learner engagement and motivation, leading to better language proficiency outcomes. Therefore, the strong assessment from both respondent groups highlights the importance of continuous program evaluation and adaptation to maintain and enhance the effectiveness of English language instruction in these contexts.

Problem No. 2: Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools with respect to the aforementioned variables?

Table 2 illustrates the significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools with respect to the aforementioned variables.

Table 2. *Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Effectiveness of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners in Select Cram Schools with Respect to the Aforementioned Variables*

Indicators	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision	Interpretation		
	Teachers	Students	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean						95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
											Lower	Upper
student engagement	-	.36402	.06153	-.18647	.06362	-.998	34	.325	FR	NS		
language proficiency	-	.62000	.10480	-.36584	.06012	-	34	.154	FR	NS		
parent satisfaction	-	.38101	.06440	-.17374	.08802	-.665	34	.510	FR	NS		
teacher qualifications	.09143	.47612	.08048	-.07212	.25498	1.136	34	.264	FR	NS		
curriculum quality	.02000	.34496	.05831	-.09850	.13850	.343	34	.734	FR	NS		

The findings revealed that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools with respect to the aforementioned variables since the p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is failed to reject, and it is found not to be significant.

The finding that there is no significant difference in the assessments of the effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners from the two respondent groups, evidenced by a p-value greater than 0.05, indicates a shared perception regarding the impact of these programs, thereby failing to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that factors influencing program effectiveness may be uniformly recognized across different demographics, implying that both groups may derive similar benefits and face comparable challenges within these educational settings.

This conclusion aligns with the study by Chen (2021), which found that students and parents often exhibit aligned expectations and assessments of supplemental language programs, reinforcing the idea that collaborative engagement among stakeholders can enhance educational outcomes. Such insights encourage educators and program developers to focus on maintaining consistency in program quality, ensuring that all participants, regardless of their backgrounds, receive equitable support in their language learning journeys.

Problem No. 3: What is the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of resource availability, financial considerations, curriculum limitations, cultural factors, and feedback mechanisms?

Table 3.1 illustrates the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of resource availability.

Table 3.1. *Mean of the Two Groups of Respondents' Assessment on the Extent of Challenges of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners in Select Cram Schools as Assessed by the Two Groups of Respondents in terms of Resource Availability*

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Overall		
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	
The after-school program provides adequate learning materials (books, worksheets, etc.) for students.	3.93	GC	3.69	GC	3.81	GC	
Classroom facilities (lighting, seating, space) are conducive to effective learning in the English program.	3.74	GC	3.58	GC	3.66	GC	
There are sufficient technological resources (computers, tablets, internet access) available for students to enhance their learning experience.	3.69	GC	3.88	GC	3.78	GC	
The program has an adequate budget to support necessary resources for students' learning needs.	3.63	GC	3.70	GC	3.66	GC	
Students have access to enough practice materials (like quizzes, assignments, and assessments) outside of classroom hours.	3.97	GC	3.71	GC	3.84	GC	
	Mean	3.74	GC	3.63	GC	3.68	GC

***Legend: 3.26-4.00- Greatly Challenge; 2.51-3.25- Challenge; 1.76-2.50 -Moderately Challenge; 1.00-1.75 - Not at all

As illustrated in the table, the two groups of respondents assessed the entire indicators as Greatly Challenge on the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of resource availability such as Students have access to enough practice materials (like quizzes, assignments, and assessments) outside of classroom hours (M=3.84); The after-school program provides adequate learning materials (books, worksheets, etc.) for students (M=3.81); There are sufficient technological resources (computers, tablets, internet access) available for students to enhance their learning experience (M=3.78); Classroom facilities (lighting, seating, space) are conducive to effective learning in the English program (M=3.66); and The program has an adequate budget to support necessary resources for students' learning needs (M=3.66). This was supported, with the overall mean value of 3.68 interpreted as greatly challenged.

The challenges faced by After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools, particularly regarding resource availability as assessed by students and teachers, imply a significant barrier to achieving optimal educational outcomes.

According to the study by Wu and Lin (2022), insufficient resources—such as access to qualified teachers, instructional materials, and technological tools—can adversely affect program effectiveness and student engagement. This suggests that addressing these resource gaps is critical for improving the overall quality of after-school language education, as enhanced support and investment in resources may lead to more effective learning experiences and better language acquisition for students.

Table 3.2 manifests the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of financial considerations.

Table 3.2. Mean of the Two Groups of Respondents' Assessment on the Extent of Challenges of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners in Select Cram Schools as Assessed by the Two Groups of Respondents in terms of Financial Considerations

	Indicators	Teachers		Students		Overall		
		Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	
1.	The cost of the after-school program is a significant barrier for many students to participate.	3.76	GC	3.76	GC	3.76	GC	
2.	Scholarships or financial aid options are available for students who cannot afford the program fees.	3.69	GC	3.68	GC	3.68	GC	
3.	The quality of the after-school program justifies its cost.	3.83	GC	3.88	GC	3.85	GC	
4.	The program offers flexible payment plans to accommodate families with financial difficulties.	3.71	GC	3.75	GC	3.73	GC	
5.	Financial constraints limit the number of students who can enroll in the after-school English program.	3.94	GC	3.75	GC	3.85	GC	
		Mean	3.80	GC	3.83	GC	3.81	GC

***Legend: 3.26-4.00- Greatly Challenge; 2.51-3.25- Challenge; 1.76-2.50 -Moderately Challenge; 1.00-1.75 – Not at all

As manifested in the table, the two groups of respondents assessed the entire indicators as Greatly Challenge on the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of financial considerations such as The quality of the after-school program justifies its cost (M=3.85); Financial constraints limit the number of students who can enroll in the after-school English program (M=3.85); The cost of the after-school program is a significant barrier for many students to participate (M=3.76); The program offers flexible payment plans to accommodate families with financial difficulties (M=3.73); and Scholarships or financial aid options are available for students who cannot afford the program fees (M=3.68). This was supported, with the overall mean value of 3.81 interpreted as greatly challenged.

The finding that the After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools is greatly challenged, particularly in terms of financial considerations as assessed by both students and parents, implies that when these programs demonstrate a clear value for the investment made, they are perceived as more beneficial and worthwhile.

This aligns with the research conducted by Chiu and Hsu (2021), which indicated that financial viability and perceived good value can significantly influence parental satisfaction and student motivation in after-school programs. Consequently, emphasizing the cost-effectiveness and positive outcomes of these English programs could enhance enrollment rates and secure continued funding and support from families, thereby reinforcing their effectiveness and sustainability in the long term.

Table 3.3 gleans the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of curriculum limitations.

As gleaned in the table, the two groups of respondents assessed the entire indicators as Greatly Challenge on the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of curriculum limitations such as The materials used in the curriculum are outdated but effectively engage students (M=3.93); The curriculum is adequately incorporate modern teaching methods and technologies (M=3.89); The program is sufficiently focused on practical language skills, such as speaking and listening (M=3.86); The after-school program does adequately prepare students for real-world English usage (M=3.85); and The after-school English program's curriculum does match the interests and needs of the students (M=3.81). This was supported, with the overall mean value of 3.87 interpreted as greatly challenged.

Table 3.3. Mean of the Two Groups of Respondents' Assessment on the Extent of Challenges of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners in Select Cram Schools as Assessed by the Two Groups of Respondents in terms of Curriculum Limitations

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Overall		
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	
The after-school English program's curriculum does match the interests and needs of the students.	3.80	GC	3.83	GC	3.81	GC	
The program is sufficiently focused on practical language skills, such as speaking and listening.	3.89	GC	3.83	GC	3.86	GC	
The curriculum is adequately incorporate modern teaching methods and technologies.	3.89	GC	3.90	GC	3.89	GC	
The after-school program does adequately prepare students for real-world English usage.	3.86	GC	3.85	GC	3.85	GC	
The materials used in the curriculum are outdated but effectively engage students.	3.97	GC	3.89	GC	3.93	GC	
	Mean	3.91	GC	3.83	GC	3.87	GC

***Legend: 3.26-4.00- Greatly Challenge; 2.51-3.25- Challenge; 1.76-2.50 -Moderately Challenge; 1.00-1.75 - Not at all

The conclusion that the After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools is greatly challenged, particularly concerning curriculum limitations as assessed by students and parents, suggests that while these programs are beneficial, there remains a critical need to address specific curricular shortcomings to optimize student learning outcomes.

This is supported by the findings of Chen (2020), which revealed that curriculum gaps, such as the lack of practical language application and integration of cultural content, can hinder overall program effectiveness. Therefore, it is imperative for program administrators to continuously evaluate and refine the curriculum to ensure it meets the diverse needs of learners, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of After-School English Programs and fostering deeper engagement and satisfaction among both students and parents.

Table 3.4 illustrates the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of cultural factors.

As illustrated in the table, the two groups of respondents assessed the entire indicators as Greatly Challenge on the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of cultural factors such as Students feel uncomfortable expressing their cultural perspectives in English during classes (M=3.92); The curriculum does provide opportunities for students to connect their cultural background with English language learning (M=3.90); The program incorporates Taiwanese cultural elements to make learning more relatable for students (M=3.86); The after-school program does encourage exploration or discussion of cultural topics related to language learning (M=3.84); and The curriculum effectively addresses the cultural differences between Taiwan and English-speaking countries (M=3.83). This was supported, with the overall mean value of 3.93 interpreted as greatly challenged.

Table 3.4. Mean of the Two Groups of Respondents' Assessment on the Extent of Challenges of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners in Select Cram Schools as Assessed by the Two Groups of Respondents in terms of Cultural Factors

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Overall		
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	
1. The curriculum effectively addresses the cultural differences between Taiwan and English-speaking countries.	3.91	GC	3.75	GC	3.83	GC	
2. The program incorporates Taiwanese cultural elements to make learning more relatable for students.	3.83	GC	3.90	GC	3.86	GC	
3. The after-school program does encourage exploration or discussion of cultural topics related to language learning.	3.77	GC	3.90	GC	3.84	GC	
4. Students feel uncomfortable expressing their cultural perspectives in English during classes.	3.97	GC	3.88	GC	3.92	GC	
5. The curriculum does provide opportunities for students to connect their cultural background with English language learning.	3.97	GC	3.84	GC	3.90	GC	
	Mean	3.94	GC	3.93	GC	3.93	GC

***Legend: 3.26-4.00- Greatly Challenge; 2.51-3.25- Challenge; 1.76-2.50 -Moderately Challenge; 1.00-1.75 - Not at all

The finding that the After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools is greatly challenged, particularly regarding cultural factors as assessed by students and parents, underscores the importance of integrating culturally relevant content into the curriculum to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes.

This aligns with the research conducted by Liu (2019), which demonstrated that incorporating local culture and context into language learning not only improves students' motivation but also fosters a deeper understanding of the language as it relates to their own experiences. Therefore, it is essential for educators to continually adapt and localize program content to reflect the cultural backgrounds

of students, ensuring that these programs not only teach English effectively but also resonate with learners on a personal and cultural level.

Table 3.5 exhibits in the table on the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of feedback mechanisms.

As exhibited in the table, the two groups of respondents assessed the entire indicators as Greatly Challenge on the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of feedback mechanisms such as Students feel encouraged to ask for clarification or further feedback on their performance (M=3.97); Feedback from peers during group activities is valued and helpful for improving language skills (M=3.97); The program includes regular assessments that help identify students' strengths and weaknesses (M=3.96); The frequency of feedback provided contributes significantly to student improvement in English (M=3.96); and The feedback provided by teachers in the program is timely and constructive (M=3.90). This was supported, with the overall mean value of 3.93 interpreted as greatly challenged.

Table 3.5. Mean of the Two Groups of Respondents' Assessment on the Extent of Challenges of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners in Select Cram Schools as Assessed by the Two Groups of Respondents in terms of Feedback Mechanisms

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. The feedback provided by teachers in the program is timely and constructive.	3.90	GC	3.91	GC	3.90	GC
2. Students feel encouraged to ask for clarification or further feedback on their performance.	3.97	GC	3.98	GC	3.97	GC
3. The program includes regular assessments that help identify students' strengths and weaknesses.	3.97	GC	3.95	GC	3.96	GC
4. Feedback from peers during group activities is valued and helpful for improving language skills.	3.97	GC	3.98	GC	3.97	GC
5. The frequency of feedback provided contributes significantly to student improvement in English.	3.94	GC	3.97	GC	3.96	GC
Mean	3.97	GC	3.88	GC	3.93	GC

***Legend: 3.26-4.00- Greatly Challenge; 2.51-3.25- Challenge; 1.76-2.50 -Moderately Challenge; 1.00-1.75 - Not at all

The greatly challenged of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools, as assessed by both students and parents in relation to feedback mechanisms, indicates that robust communication channels and responsive feedback practices are crucial for maximizing educational outcomes. This notion is supported by the study conducted by Hattie and Timperley (2007), which found that effective feedback enhances student learning by providing specific information on performance and guiding future improvement. Consequently, it becomes imperative for educators to implement systematic feedback mechanisms that not only gather insights from learners and their families but also ensure that this feedback is utilized to refine curricula and teaching methods. Such practices will foster a more collaborative learning environment where students feel heard and empowered, ultimately leading to even greater program effectiveness.

Table 3.6 illustrates the composite mean of the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents.

Table 3.6. Composite Mean of the Two Groups of Respondents' Assessment on the Extent of Challenges of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners in Select Cram Schools

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
resource availability	3.74	GC	3.63	GC	3.68	GC
financial considerations	3.80	GC	3.83	GC	3.81	GC
curriculum limitations	3.91	GC	3.83	GC	3.87	GC
cultural factors	3.97	GC	3.84	GC	3.90	GC
feedback mechanisms	3.97	GC	3.88	GC	3.93	GC
Mean	3.82	GC	3.87	GC	3.85	GC

***Legend: 3.26-4.00- Greatly Challenge; 2.51-3.25- Challenge; 1.76-2.50 -Moderately Challenge; 1.00-1.75 - Not at all

As illustrated in the table on the composite mean of the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of feedback mechanisms (M=3.93); cultural factors (M=3.90); curriculum limitations (M=3.87); financial considerations (M=3.81); and resource availability (M=3.68). This was supported with a composite mean of 3.85 interpreted as greatly challenged.

The finding that the composite mean of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools is greatly challenged, as assessed by both students and parents, implies the critical role of tailored educational approaches in fostering language

acquisition. This aligns with the research of Wong and Chen (2020), which highlighted that culturally responsive teaching significantly enhances student engagement and learning outcomes. Therefore, it is essential for program developers and educators to consider the unique cultural and contextual needs of Taiwanese learners when designing and implementing these programs. By doing so, they can further optimize the effectiveness of language instruction and ensure that it resonates with both students and their families, thereby supporting a more enriching educational experience.

Problem No. 4: Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools with respect to the aforementioned variables?

Table 4 illustrates the significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools with respect to the aforementioned variables.

Table 4. *Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of Challenges of After-School English Programs Among Taiwanese Learners in Select Cram Schools with Respect to the Aforementioned Variables*

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Paired Differences		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision	Interpretation	
			Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference						
				Mean						Lower
Teachers	Students									
resource availability	-.05714	.59125	.09994	-.26025	.14596	-.572	34	.571	FR	NS
financial considerations	.08571	.65849	.11131	-.14049	.31191	.770	34	.447	FR	NS
curriculum limitations	-.08571	.50709	.08571	-.25991	.08848	-	34	.324	FR	NS
cultural factors	.02857	.29563	.04997	-.07298	.13012	.572	34	.571	FR	NS
feedback mechanisms	-.10629	.21124	.03571	-.17885	-.03372	-	34	.005	R	S
								2.977		

The findings revealed that there is significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools with respect to feedback mechanisms since the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is found to be significant.

The finding of a significant difference in the assessment of challenges related to feedback mechanisms in After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners suggests that varying perceptions between students and parents can impact the effectiveness of these programs. With a p-value less than 0.05 leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis, it indicates a need for program developers to consider these differing viewpoints to enhance feedback systems. This aligns with the study by Chen (2021), which highlighted that effective communication and tailored feedback strategies are crucial in addressing learner needs and improving educational outcomes in similar contexts. Therefore, fostering collaborative dialogue between students, parents, and educators could mitigate the identified challenges and lead to more successful After-School English Programs.

Problem No. 5: Is there a significant relationship between the level of effectiveness and the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools?

Table 5 illustrates the significant relationship between the level of effectiveness and the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools.

Table 5. *Relationship Between the Level of Effectiveness and the Extent of Challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese Learners in Select Cram Schools*

Indicators		Pearson r	Sig	Ho	VI
Level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs	Extent of challenges of After-School English Programs	-.057	.628	FR	NS

***Legend: FR-Failed to Reject; R-Rejected; NS-Not Significant; S-Significant

The findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between the level of effectiveness and the extent of challenges of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools since the p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is failed to reject, and it is found to be not significant. Also, it has a Pearson r correlation of -.057.

The findings indicate that there is no significant relationship between the level of effectiveness and the extent of challenges faced by Taiwanese learners in After-School English Programs at select Cram schools, as demonstrated by a p-value greater than 0.05 and a Pearson correlation coefficient of -.057. This suggests that the challenges encountered by students do not significantly hinder or enhance their perceptions of program effectiveness, implying that other factors may play a more critical role in shaping their learning experiences. The lack of a significant correlation mirrors the results of a related study by Lin (2020), which found that external challenges, such as time constraints and motivation levels, did not directly correlate with perceived program effectiveness among

learners. As a result, educators and program coordinators should consider examining additional variables beyond challenges—such as instructional quality and engagement strategies—to better understand and improve the overall effectiveness of these English learning programs.

Conclusions

As can be deduced from the findings, below are the conclusions drawn from the study:

Student engagement, parent satisfaction, teacher qualifications, curriculum quality, and language proficiency were some of the metrics used to evaluate the after-school English programs, all of which pointed to their great effectiveness.

The assessment of the two groups of respondents on the level of effectiveness of After-School English Programs among Taiwanese learners in select Cram schools reveals no significant in terms of student engagement, parent satisfaction, teacher qualifications, curriculum quality, and language proficiency.

Feedback mechanisms, cultural factors, curriculum limitations, financial considerations, and resource availability were all major challenges in assessing after-school English programs for Taiwanese students at chosen Cram schools.

Feedback mechanisms substantially affect the evaluation of the two respondent groups of the issues faced by after-school English programs among Taiwanese learners at certain Cram schools.

The efficacy of after-school English programs is unrelated to the difficulties encountered by Taiwanese students in select Cram schools.

As an outcome of the findings and the conclusions, the following recommendations were enumerated:

Teachers may implement activities that promote student engagement such as games, group projects, and presentations to make learning enjoyable and relevant.

Teachers may tailor support and resources that cater to individual learning needs, allowing students to progress at their own pace.

Teachers may establish a system for providing constructive feedback to students on their language skills, enabling them to understand their strengths and areas for improvement.

Students may take part in vocabulary activities such as word games, discussions, and group projects and may practice incorporating newly learned vocabulary into writing assignments.

Administrators may offer ongoing training sessions that focus on innovative teaching methods, classroom management techniques, and the integration of technology to enhance lesson delivery.

Administrators may encourage teachers to collaborate on lesson planning and share successful strategies, creating a supportive community focused on student outcomes.

Parallel study may be conducted using different variables.

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